

**ROBERT F KENNEDY WAS A VICTIM OF INTELLIGENT HOMICIDE: FORENSIC
AND MATHEMATICAL EVIDENCE**

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ABSTRACT

Robert F Kennedy was shot and mortally wounded in the service pantry of the Ambassador Hotel, Los Angeles on June 5th, 1968. A Palestinian immigrant Sirhan Sirhan was convicted of murder. Notably, some new information questioned the original LAPD investigation by highlighting inconsistencies based on updated acoustic, ballistic, and forensic data. **Objective:** To answer, "Was RFK a victim of "Intelligent homicide.?" **Method:** We conducted a literature search of RFK assassination Identified 14 publications as Informative. We applied the probability theory to RFK research data to project odds of certainty that RFK was a victim of Intelligent homicide. **Results:** There are 18 observations consistent with Robert F Kennedy was a victim of intelligent homicide and inconsistent with that he was not, suggesting that Robert F Kennedy was a victim of Intelligent homicide. The odds of this conclusion being correct is %99.99. **Discussion:** Forensic evidence indicated that the killer shot was fired from behind and inches close to RFK; hence, Sirhan facing RFK and did not get close to him was not the killer. Thane Eugene Cesar, the security guard who stood right behind RFK was the actual killer evident by a dramatic death scene photo of the guards bow tie in RFK's grip. Surprisingly, Cesar escaped adequate scrutiny during the LAPD investigation. In the spirit of science and governmental integrity a new investigation is warranted. LAPD destroyed vital evidence and Sirhan a victim of MKULTRA brain washing / hypnoprogramming was convicted of a crime he did not commit consistent with intelligent homicide. Intelligent homicide seems to be a major unrecognized threat to democracy. A UN resolution to declare GEA - as a crime against humanity is worthy of consideration. Conclusion: Robert F Kennedy was a victim of Intelligent homicide.

KEYWORDS: The odds of this conclusion being correct is %99.99.**INTRODUCTION**

At 12:16 AM on Wednesday, June 5th, 1968, Senator Robert F Kennedy was shot and mortally wounded in the service pantry of the Ambassador Hotel, Los Angeles.^[1,2] A Palestinian immigrant Sirhan Sirhan was convicted of murder.^[1,2] In the last several decades new information has emerged both In support of and against the original verdict of Sirhan Sirhan being the lone killer of Robert F Kennedy.^[1,3]

Notably, some new information questioned the original LAPD investigation by highlighting inconsistencies based on updated acoustic, ballistic, and forensic data. In the past decade forensic research revealed several assassinations meticulously planned and executed with no provable trace of crime. These government sanctioned

assassinations will be referred to as intelligent homicides in this paper.

OBJECTIVE

To answer, "Was RFK a victim of Intelligent homicide.?"

METHOD

We conducted a literature search of RFK assassination Identified 14 publications as Informative and applied the probability theory to project odds of certainty that RFK. was a victim of intelligent homicide.

The probability of a physically possible observation to be correct exponentially increases by each supporting evidence and can be expressed as an equation $R = 1/2^X$. R representing the probability of random occurrence and x

the number of diverse evidence consistent with the observation and inconsistent with the observation.

This equation is based upon the premise that each supporting evidence is a hypothesis, a logical inference from observing facts from which consequences may be deduced with a 50% chance of being correct, and therefore the final outcome would be the same as the probability of random occurrence in flipping a coin. Hence it would be like heads coming up at consecutive times.

As long as it is fair play without tricks, it does not matter who flips the coin.

RESULTS

18 observations consistent with Robert F Kennedy was a victim of Intelligent homicide. and inconsistent with Robert F Kennedy was not, suggesting that Robert F Kennedy was a victim of Intelligent homicide.

1. Robert F Kennedy was fatally wounded by 3 bullets, five people suffered injuries and two bullets struck the wall suggesting 10 bullets were fired,; hence there were more than one shooter^[1,3] (mage A). This finding ruled out a lone killer alleged by LAPD.
2. The killer shot was fired from behind and inches close to RFK^[1,3] (Image A).
3. Sirhan faced RFK and did not get close to him. The killer shot was fired from behind (image A). Thus, Sirhan was not the killer.
4. Acoustical evidence indicated that there were ten shots during the assassination.^[5] Thus, Sirhan was not the lone shooter.
5. The gunshots came from two opposite directions.^[5] Thus, Sirhan was not the lone shooter.
6. Sirhan was convicted of a crime he did not commit consistent with 2, 3.,4,5.
7. The killer shot was fired from behind and inches close to RFK's skull. Thane Eugene Cesar, the security guard was right behind RFK^[3,4] (Image B).
8. RFK had grabbed the guard's bow tie; hence Cesar was the most likely candidate to be the killer. (Image C)
9. In May 2008, Dr Daniel Brown, associate professor in Psychology at Harvard Medical School a world renowned authority on hypnosis after three years of testing and interviewing Mr. Siran stated:" it is my opinion that Sirhan did not act under his own volition and knowledge or intention at the time of the assassination. And further, that the system of mind control which was imposed upon him has also made it impossible for him to recall, under hypnosis or consciously, many critical details of actions and events leading up to and at the time of the shooting in the pantry of the Ambassador Hotel).^[6]
10. Sirhan Sirhan recorded II In his note book god help me please help me salvo Di De Salvo Die Salvo without ever knowing the Boston strangler. This was consistent with the observation that Srhan Sirhan was hypnoprogrammed by Dr Bryant/CA expert on hypnoprogramming.^[6]
11. Dr William Joseph Bryan / CIA MKULTRA mind control project who hypnotized the Boston Strangler died suddenly soon before he was summoned to testify before the House Select Committee on assassinations.^[6]
12. Stanislav Pruzynnski,a reporter at Montreal gazette tape CSA-K123 StusI-4837 JUNE1968,: 9 t0 11 shots were fired.^[7]
13. Thane Eugene Cesar a security guard for Ace Security Services acknowledged his intense dislike of RFK and his political views.^[8]
14. Thane Eugene Cesar greatly benefited financially from the assassination.
15. Thane Eugene Cesar repeatedly disappeared from public eye before relocating in the Philippines where he died.^[8]
16. Cesar stated that he owned a.22-caliber Harrington & Richardson pistol, and he showed it to LAPD sergeant P. E. O'Steen on June 24, 1968.[17] But when the LAPD interviewed Cesar three years later, he claimed that he had sold the gun before the assassination to a man named Jim Yoder. William W. Turner tracked down Yoder in October 1972. Yoder still had the receipt for the H&R pistol, dated September 6, 1968, and bearing Cesar's signature, indicating that Cesar had sold the pistol three months after Kennedy's assassination, contradicting his 1971 claim that he had sold the weapon months before.^[8]
17. LAPD did not investigate Thane Eugene Cesar, the prime suspect of RFK's murder.
18. LAPD destroyed vital evidence.^[9]

Robert F Kennedy was a victim of GEA. The odds of this conclusion being correct is %99.999.

Image A

RFK POSTMORTEM: NOTE SKULL INJURY CONSISTENT WITH A SHOT FIRED FROM BEHIND.

Image B.

SECURITY GUARD WITH BOW TIE NEXT TO RFK MOMENTS BEFORE THE FATAL SHOTS

Image C.

NOTE BOW TIE ON THE GROUND AND IN RFK'S GRIP

TABLE 1

Evidence Consistent with Cover Up by LAPD

- A. No investigation of Cesar despite evidence of him as the most likely candidate who shot the killer bullet.
- B. Sudden death of Dr Bryant before testimony before the house select committee on assassination.
- C. Destruction of evidence by LAPD.
- D. Dismissal of forensic acoustic postmortem data by LAPD.
- E. LAPD diagrammatic explanation of the shooting contradicted by the sworn testimony of witnesses.

TABLE 2

Evidence Consistent with Two Shooters

1. Acoustic evidence of shots from opposite directions.
2. Acoustic evidence of 10 or more shots.
3. Forensic evidence of back entry killer shot.
4. Witness reports of ss and guards firing.

TABLE 3

Evidence Consistent with SS was not the killer

1. The killer shot was fired from behind and Sirhan faced RFK.
2. The killer shot was fired from close range and Sirhan never got close

TABLE 4

Evidence Consistent with Cesar was the killer.

1. Thane Eugene Cesar acknowledged his intense dislike of RFK and his political views.
2. Thane Eugene Cesar greatly benefited financially from the assassination.

3. Thane Eugene Cesar repeatedly disappeared from public eye before relocating in the Philippines where he died.
4. Cesar lied: Cesar stated that he owned a .22-caliber Harrington & Richardson pistol, and he showed it to LAPD sergeant P. E. O'Steen on June 24, 1968. But when the LAPD interviewed Cesar three years later, he claimed that he had sold the gun before the assassination to a man named Jim Yoder. William W. Turner tracked down Yoder in October 1972. Yoder still had the receipt for the H&R pistol, dated September 6, 1968, and bearing Cesar's signature, indicating that Cesar had sold the pistol three months after Kennedy's assassination.
5. Cesar's tie in the grips of RFK. image
6. The killer shot was fired from behind and close range, a perfect match for Cesar.

DISCUSSION

New evidence supported by forensic medical acoustic and ballistic data is inconsistent with the hypothesis that Sirhan Sirhan is the lone killer of Robert F Kennedy.

Forensic evidence indicated that the killer shot was fired from behind and inches close to RFK; hence, Sirhan facing RFK and did not get close to him, was not the killer. Furthermore Caesar, the security guard who stood right behind RFK owned a .22 Harrington & Richardson pistol, acknowledged his intense dislike of RFK, financially benefited from his murder was the actual killer. He never became a key subject of interest during the LAPD investigation.

It seems that, multiple LAPD investigative flaws may represent willful violations of common standards of criminal investigation.

In essence, a cluster of very unusual failures let allegations that Sirhan Sirhan was RFK's lone killer.

Worthy of emphasis is the collective picture of an orchestrated crime that can be easily misperceived as conspiratorial by a narrow review of individual pieces of data.

RFK's death represents a dark page in the annals of the Vietnam war that contributed to the deaths of 58,000 Americans, 1.5 million Vietnamese, John F Kennedy, Martin Luther King., John Lennon, Lee H Oswald, Jack Ruby, and many others.

In the spirit of science and governmental integrity a new investigation is warranted.

Intelligent homicide is a major unrecognized threat to democracy.

A UN resolution to declare Intelligent homicide, as a crime against humanity is worthy of consideration.

CONCLUSION

Robert F Kennedy was a victim of Intelligent homicide. The odds of this conclusion being correct is %99.999.

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